

NAXALISM AND ADMINISTRATION
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Abstract: -

Naxalism is the biggest challenge for the internal security of the country. This has not only affected tribal areas but also has its impacts of urban society and administration. Naxalism has created many challenges in front of system, administration and society. In the democratic country like India, there are many serious issues, but the Naxal problem has put question mark on the security of entire country. Entire administration is put on toes to tackle the Naxalism issue. In addition to this, Indian society which by and large believe in peace of co-existence is also facing serious heat of the issue. Naxalism on one hand has created negative impact on administration and society, while on the other hand there are some positive impacts too. When we see at administration in Naxal affected areas, we can easily sense that the issue has made difference in the working style of administration in these areas. This positive impact can be attributed to Naxal issue in the region.

Keywords: - *Naxalism, Administration, Movement*

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Introduction:-
Background of Naxal movement

A perfect definition of Naxalism is a difficult task as the name Naxal itself is derived from the village Naxalbari in Siliguri area in Darjiling district of West Bengal. Youths in the area revolted against the exploitation of *Jamindars* (Landlords) in the region. They killed Jamindars, looted their godowns and distributed the grains and food amongst poor. As the incident happened in the Naxalbari village, the movement which flourished later also got the name from the very village, that is Naxalism.

The area of 207. Sq.km. at the base of Himalaya in Siliguri region in the Darjiling district of

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West Bengal is considered as Naxal affected area. Various tribes such as Santhal, Munda, Orao, Rajwanshi resided here and were exploited hugely by local Kulka (Jamindars). Youths inspired by the thoughts of Mao, namely, Charu Muzumdar, Kanu Sanyal, K.P.Gopalan, Naga Reddy, Jungle Santhal raised voice against this exploitation and decided to revolt. If people are ready for revolution and government is weak, in that case, instead of wasting time in economic reforms and without wasting time on democratic procedures, priority should be given to armed revolt, insisted Char Muzumdar.

On March 2, 1967, clash occurred between police and local tribal agitators in the Naxalbari village in which one tribal youth got killed. This gave impetus to Naxal movement. In May, 1967 armed youths, inspired by the thoughts of Mao, did revolt in Naxalbari village. Jamindar was killed, his godown was looted and grains were distributed in common people. These rebels were raising slogans such as 'acquiring power through armed revolt', 'Mao Tse Tung is our leader and idol' etc. This armed agitation started triggering similar situation in surrounding villages. At the beginning, police neglected the thing considering it as local class struggle. But, similar incidents went on rise in the vicinity. Incidents such as attacks on houses and godowns of Zamindars also increased. The center and inspiration of all such things was Naxalbari village. All this violent incidents continued for almost 52 days. Power acquisition through armed revolt, Maoist philosophy behind it and neighbouring Chinese border caught the attention of entire nation towards the agitation. Sensing its threat, state government initiated strict action and started combing operation against the rebel.

The movement spread to different parts of the country like a forest fire. Many students in the country who were dreaming about new world and new societal order got attracted towards this movement. In the traditional agriculture economy, all political controls were in the hands of landlords and hence to change the situation, armed struggle was the only option, felt rebels. According to the statement of Mao, that is, 'If some revolution is occurring, there needs a revolutionary party there', the extremists founded the Communist Party of India (Marxist-Leninist) on Apr 22, 1969.

Aims of Naxal movement:

- Mounting struggle against government by uniting farmers in the rural parts.
- Demolishing the landlord system from the country.

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- Developing a strong base of Naxal movement in rural parts.
- Armed struggle against police.

This was the main aim of the movement and end of class enemies was the main formula. Violence in the Naxalism movement reached its pinnacle in the period of 1970 to mid-1971. Around 4000 cases of violence were registered in entire country in this period. Highest 3500 cases were registered in West Bengal, 220 in Bihar and 70 in Andhra Pradesh.

Taking account of increasing violence, Union government with the help of army and local police, implemented a special secret campaign from July 1 to Aug 15, 1971 with the code name of 'Operation Steepechase'. In this operation, many naxalists were arrested and their arms were seized. On July 10, 1972, Charu Muzumdar, founder of Naxam movement was arrested. Within few days, he passed away in Lal Bazaar jail and the Naxal movement was divided in four different parts.

After the death of Charu Muzumdar, the leadership of the movement came to Mahadev Mukherjee and Sharma. They reunited the movement and made it more violent. During the same period, it spread in states like Andhra Pradesh, Bihar, West Bengal, Punjab, Kerala, TamilNadu, Maharashtra and other small states.

Naxam movement got vigour when Communist Party of India Marxist-Leninist, People's War group was formed in Andhra Pradesh on Apr 20, 1980 under the leadership of Kondapalli Sitaramayya. During the same period, The Maoist, Communist Center was formed in Bihar by Prashant Bose, Amulya Sen, Kaati Chatterjee and others. Shamsheersingh Sheri started separate Naxal movement in Punjab.

It is said that, People's War Group redistributed around 5 lakh acre land in Andhra Pradesh. People witnessed things actually happening after the intervention of Naxals, which were earlier only spoken and promised by elected governments. This developed support for the movement among common people and they named Naxals as 'Gorakaladora' (Friends of Forests).

Revolutionary writers in the cultural wing of PWG contributed hugely to make the Naxal ideology acceptable among people. Warwara Rao is one of the most influential name in this category. This group spread its activities beyond the borders and also around state borders of Rayalseema, Maharashtra, Madhya Pradesh and Tamil Nadu. PWG in its 2001 Congress gave

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permission of using all modern arms, to militarize the movement which increased its level of violence.

Presently, according to Union Home Ministry, PWG and Maoist Communist Center is increasing its influence in Tamil Nadu, Karnataka, Kerala.

According to report of Institute of Conflict Management, Naxal movement has its spread in 14 states and 165 districts. Naxal ability to create violence has increased vastly due to availability of modern arms and technology of using explosives. Presently, Naxal movement has 6500, AK47, AK56, LMG, SLR, 303 rifles and other such arms. As declared on Oct 14,2004, different Naxal groups in all parts of country including PWG and Maoist Communist Center and Communist Party of India (Maoist) has been formed which has given new boost to the movement. This group has introduced itself as the revolutionary group in India. Previously a small movement has now extended its reach from Pashupati to Tirpuathi in Red Corridor.

According to report of Union Intelligence departments, 2018, some of the districts in India are sensitive from Naxal point of view which include Vishakhapattanam in Seemandhra, Bamakshi, Kondagundam in Telangana, Jamui, Aurangabad, Sitabhari, Gaya in Bihar, Ranchi, Hajaribagh, Chatara, Palam, Lohandanga, Garawa, Simadega, Katihar, Giridoh, Kokarama, Bokaro, Dhanbad, East and west Sinhabhoom, Nuti, Ramgadh, Saatikala districts in Jharkhand Kanker, Bastar, Bijapur, Dantewada, Saraguja, Katihar, Narayanapur, Rajanandgaon, in Chattisagarh as well as Katepuri, Malkangiri in Orissa and Gadchiroli and Gondiya districts in Maharashtra.

Supporting organizations of Naxal movements

Naxal movement in present situation has its operations in 14 states and around 165 districts in the country. Before, 2005 it has different groups working in different states which CPI (different groups), People Liberation Guerilla Army, CPI-ML Janshakti, CPI-ML Naxalbari, CPI-ML PWG, MCC, PLA, MCPM, RCP, TNLA and other factions. All these groups came together and formed Communist Party of India (Maoist) in 2004. This organization has got support within and outside country which include ULFA (United Liberation Front of Assam), NSCN in Nagaland, NPA, PBSP, CPN (Maoist), CIC, SIMI in India as well as LTTE in Sri Lanka, government sponsored extremists organizations in China, ISI, Lashkar-E-Tayaba,

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Harkat-Ul-Jehad Islami (Huji) in Pakistan, Moists organizations in Nepal, Revolutionary Potential Movement in south, Left wing extremists groups in Philippines etc.

Influence of Naxal movement on administration.

Naxals attract attention of government by anti-government actions in their region of influence. All these actions are violent which affect common people and administration and put question mark on law and order. These violent actions typically include attacks on Police, destroying government properties to protest against the govebemnt, To set timber depots on fire, hampering Tendu leaves collection process, setting a fire vehicles of government or contractors, Setting a fire vehicles, furniture and records of government, destroying roads and bridges using land mines etc. Using these methods Naxals cause huge losses to government and private assets.

Looting arms by attacking police stations, robbing materials from forest employees, robberies at the houses of rich people, extortion, killing suspected informers of Police, killing sarpanc, police Patils, Gramsevaks, teachers and other people's representatives who help administration are some of the regular activites of Naxals. The motive behind these acts is to treat people so that nobody could stand against Naxals and in support of police and administration. To hamper government and police works, Naxals have been witnessed doing things like blocking roads using cut trees, destroying Solar lamps and plates in villages, stop school functioning, destroying school buildings and other such works in Naxal affected areas. This makes government to take action against Naxals and stay alert while working in Naxal affected areas. On the other hand, inactiveness and lack of sensitivity for its responsibility on the part of government machinery helps Naxals to increase the area of their work. Hence, Naxals more often try to highlight inefficiency of the government. Therefore, administration needs to working with alertness all the while. In Naxal affected areas, problems can be related different government departments, but responsibility of providing solutions for those lies mostly with police department. For example, if borewell or electricity supply is stopped, fair price shops is closed, Talathis, Gramsevak or teachers are not coming on time at their workplaces, all these issues are concerned with various departments. But locals do not contact those departments for resolving these issues, instead they reach to nearby police centers and register their complaints. The complaint is then forwarded to Superintendent of Police office

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who in turn convey it personally to Collector office which then work out the solution to resolve the complaint. Collector office directs concern section to solve the complaint and asks to file in report about the work. It again contact the complainant through police help center, takes information about the work done, informs about it to Superintendent of Police office . This means police department acts as bridge between all government departments.

One can see that, in Naxal affected area, administration is always in active mode and all departments need to work with all alertness and efficiency. Due to presence of Naxalists, normal lacunae in administration are not seen in Naxal affected areas. At some places, Naxals are seen threatening government officials and employees for the benefit of common people. Occasionally, they punish employees too. Hence, with the fear of losing lives, many employees work in with efficiency and urgency in these areas. Administration also take repeated reviews of development works and facilities in the region to improve those. This makes administration efficient in their works. Presence of Naxals have also affected positively to curb local corruption to some extent. Efficient administration in this region is the result of Naxal movement.

Along with this positive impact, negative impact of Naxal movement can also be seen on the administration.

- Administration faces many obstacles in the implementation of government policies due to presence of Naxal movement.
- As Naxals target the administrative officials directly and even attack them, many officials and employees are seen working under immense pressure and fear.

References: -

Dasgupta, Biplav (1974): The Naxal Movement, Bombay: R.K.Publication.

Dasgupta (1994): Naxalite Movement, Bombay: Allied Publication.

Ghosh Sharkar (1990): Naxalite Movement, Delhi: Ashish Publishing.

सुहास कुलकर्णी, मिलिंद चंपानेरकर 'यांनी घडवलं सहस्रक' पुणे रोहन प्रकाशन 2003.

अनुराग मिश्रा संपादित योजना मासिक नक्षल विशेषांक फ्रेब्रु. 2007

मिलिंद शेठे संपादित 'सांस्कृतिक वार्तापत्र' नक्षलवाद विशेषांक ऑग. 2010.

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